

The Role of Electronic Human Resource Management Practices in Industry

M K Ganeshan

Ph.D Scholar, Alagappa Institute of Management, School of Management, Alagappa University, Tamil Nadu, India
Corresponding Author: M K Ganeshan
Email: mkganeshanmba@gmail.com

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Abstract

Electronic human resource management is increasingly being used to replace face-to-face human resource management tasks. E-HRM aids the HR function in developing dynamic and operational capabilities, as well as improving the efficiency of human resource management. The organizations are supposed to assist people in better understanding E-HRM in a systematic and comprehensive manner. With the rapid advancement of science and technology, particularly the use of the internet and computer technology, significant changes have occurred in our economy, society, and culture. With the development of these technologies in recent years, a new form of human resource technology known as electronic human resource management has emerged. Human resource departments can use this application to find new ways to contribute to the success of the firm. Human resources are the most expensive resource in every firm; as a result, they must be managed carefully. The major goal of human resources is to ensure that a company hires the proper people, with the right knowledge, management skills, proficiency abilities, and grace competences. In most industries, finding the right candidate for the correct job at the factual time is a trial. Those who are driven and committed to attaining the organization's current and strategic goals. Make practice provides a more efficient and planned manner of working to achieve the aims in this application. As a result, human resource operations have the opportunity to build a new platform for committing to corporate success. In this sense, today's knowledge-based economy has a great demand. Organizations who want to optimize their employees' potential and productivity should use this application. This application can also assist in achieving a goal that HRM information systems are working towards.

Keywords

Human Resource, e-HRM, Organization, Technology, Applications.

Introduction

With the rapid advancement of science and technology, particularly the use of the internet and computer technology, significant changes have occurred in our economy, society, and culture. With the introduction of these technologies in recent years, a new generation of HR technology, well-known as electronic human resource management has emerged. E-HRM is a relatively recent word for HRM that is assisted by information technology, particularly through the use of web technology. The word E-HRM was devised in the 1990s to describe the use of the internet or intranet to undertake HRM activities. E-HRM is well-defined as the practice of information technology to link and provision at most dual specific or combined performs in executing HRM operations self-possessed. Because electronic human resource management allows human resource functions to establish new avenues for contributing to corporate performance, it is predicted that E-HRM will enable HR practitioners to work in a more efficient and strategic manner. The lack of integration of e-HRM systems and data as a resource were recognized as two major technological difficulties by interviewees. An approachable is infrastructure, e-HRM orientation or configuration, and the utilization of data as a resource was among the e-HRM technological problems. Technology through HR is responsible for a variety of concerns, but the most pressing challenges that HR departments face today are recruitment, retention, and motivation, as well as leadership development and corporate working culture. Addressing these difficulties has become a continuous and time-consuming exercise as HR attempts to transfer on the way to a more strategic position.

Objective of the study

1. To study the concept of electronic human resource management practices, human resource, and management in the current scenario of industry.
2. To know about the categories of electronic human resource management practices in the organization.
3. To study the various tools and roles of electronic human resource management practices in the industry.

Categories of Electronic Human Resource Management

There are three kinds of E-HRM. These are described individually as operational, relational and transformational. Operational E-HRM is associated with administrative functions-payroll and employee personal data for instance. The operational type of HRM provides the choice between asking employees to keep their own personal data up to date through an HR website or to have an administrative force in place to do this. Relational E-HRM is related with supporting business processes by ways of training, recruitment, performance management and so forth. As to relational HRM, there is the choice between supporting recruitment and selection through a web-based application or using a paper-based approach through advertisements, paper-based application forms and letters. Transformational E-HRM is related with strategic HR activities known as knowledge management, strategic re-orientation. As to transformational HRM, it is possible to create a change-ready workforce through an integrated set of web-based tools that enables the workforce to develop in line with the company's strategic choices or to have paper-based materials.

Tools or Activities of Electronic Human Resource Management Practices

- E-Employee profile
- E-Recruitment – Online
- E-Selection
- E-Learning/web based training- Audio, video, video conferencing, computer, tablets and mobile devices, blogging.
- Classical and virtual learning
- E-Training
- E- Performance Management system- Organization's benefits, managers benefits, employees benefits
- E- Compensation
- Grievance Tracking and analysis
- E- Leave, attendance system, payroll, career development, idea and creativity exchange system, assessment system, welfare system
- Anywhere, anytime access
- Eliminate majority of HR paperwork

Role of Electronic Human Resource Management Practices

Reducing Cost

Human Resource costs are a crucial component of HR accounting. A cost is a sacrifice made in order to get a desired benefit or service. This indicates that every cost has two parts: an "expense" and an "asset." HR cost-cutting strategies or human resources department cost-cutting strategies, new health-care providers should be priced. One option is to shop around and compare plan prices. Implement risk-reduction techniques. Use imagination. Re-evaluate your salary levels. Remove any programs that aren't required. Take into account outsourcing services. Cost reductions will result in more money being available for labor welfare programmes, which will strengthen the management relationship. HR has a number of smart cost-cutting methods. Star performers should be hired and kept: When it comes to cutting expenses, an organization's ability to attract, hire, and retain excellent personnel is crucial. Make training and mentorship a top priority. Consolidate activities, eliminate repetitive procedures, and promote talent mobility.

Improving HR Services

The practice of web-based information or knowledge to keep employees records and advance human resources techniques, such as job analysis, staffing, selection, training, routine management, and benefit. There are several of ways that web based information or data may service HR work improved. Human resources and human experience are improved by technology automation frees up time for human interaction, provides more data, connects employees around the world, and enhances personalization. HR should assess compensation and benefits, communicate and build a strong culture, develop talent from within, implement wellness initiatives, manage compliance, embrace technology and analytics, and understand the organization's strategic goals to improve and maximize HR services.

Improving Strategic Orientation

Acting in accordance with the organization's priorities, strategy, or vision is referred to as strategic orientation in management. The desire to contribute to the direction of the organization is my primary motive. Being contemplative might help you strengthen your strategic direction. Make time for thinking in your everyday schedule. Be open-minded and inventive. Make an effort to increase your present levels of curiosity. Make an effort to socialize. Make time to talk to people from both inside and outside the company. Set priorities and work quickly. The ultimate goal of digital competency is to increase enterprise organizational performance in order to deliver value.

Impact of Globalization

Organizations have been forced to participate in local and international marketplaces as a result of globalization, in order to increase the quality of commerce and the level of business operations. Because they must deal with daily changes and balance internal and external difficulties, HRM must focus on practical challenges that affect their business. Globalization has an impact on businesses that compete for clients that have high performance, quality, and cost expectations. Globalization also puts pressure on HRM to adapt to changing company needs and offer better value.

Lack of Clear Practices

Technological advancements can have a significant impact on an organization's human resources department. It enables the business to strengthen its internal processes, core competencies, target markets, and overall organizational structure. Human Resources will be more efficient and effective as a result of this. HR practices have an impact on the organization's performance. HRM techniques include improving employees' abilities, dedication, and effort in order to improve organizational performance. Immaterial contentment is influenced by HRM practices, which has a favorable impact on the organization's success.

Improving Performance

Make a strategy that includes well-defined policies and processes. In addition to email, build up communication solutions to keep in touch with remote personnel. Executives or HR professionals should be taught how to perfect their performance in order to carry out personnel accountability activities. Departments and divisions in organizations are one of the primary HR experts who affect the design of marketing strategies. Providing the company with strategy development training and resources: "We need to empower our personnel to accomplish their jobs."

Making Strategic Decision

Employee analysis is carried out by strategic HR. It determines the steps that must be taken in order to boost their company's value. The findings of this study are also used in strategic human resource management. To develop HR approaches for dealing with employee flaws. The ability to update records is provided by E-HR. Using these records, you can make quick decisions. Organizational skills were improved because to computerized HR. Members of the organization in making more rewarding and meaningful decisions on time. Employee security is one of the best HR initiatives. Self-managed approach and selective employment of the suitable personnel. Effective teams, as well as equitable and performance-based compensation, are important strategic tasks. The development of relevant skills,

the establishment of a flat and egalitarian organizational structure, and the provision of information to those who require it.

HR Policy and Practices

The enterprise's computerized human resources management process, as well as its resources strategies, policies, and practices. The most widely used e-HRM functions in current practices are: E-HR Planning, acquiring HR such as recruitment and selection, developing HR such as training and development, career management, rewarding HR such as performance evaluation, compensation and benefits, and protecting HR such as health and safety.

Information Technology Solution

The use of technology to keep employee records and improve human resources procedures, such as job analysis, recruitment, selection, training, performance management, and compensation, is known as electronic human resources management. E-HRM is the use of technology in HR practices to make it easier for employees and employers to engage. It keeps track of payroll, personal information about employees, performance management, training, recruitment, and strategy orientation. HR managers use information technology to track employee performance and evaluate employee feedback for organizational advantage. HR managers have access to a variety of hardware and software applications that allow them to assess employee performance and set performance standards.

Technological Innovation

HR innovation is the use of new ideas, methods, and technology to better fulfill the industry's and its workforce's ever-changing needs. It's more about anticipating future wants and conditions than it is about reacting to a changing current situation. HR departments are changing the way they communicate with employees, store files, and measure employee performance as a result of technological advancements. When used correctly, technology may help HR operations become more efficient. When used incorrectly, it might obstruct the management of an industry's human resources. HR technology is used in the human resources business to recruit, hire, retain, and sustain personnel, as well as to assist workforce administration and optimize workforce organization. HR technology also gives managers the decision-making tools they need to make better HR decisions. It has the potential to expand the total of work hours in a daytime. It can also be used to modify old-style work environments in addition to make them more flexible, allowing people to be more liberated. HRM can improve its people strategy with the help of technology.

Conclusion

An HR department's job is to increase employee productivity while also protecting the organization from any problems that develop in the workplace. Compensation and benefits, recruitment, dismissal, and staying up to date on any regulations that may affect the organization and its employees are all part of HR's responsibilities. An HR department's job is to increase employee productivity while also protecting the organization from any difficulties that develop in the workplace. Compensation and benefits, recruitment, dismissal, and staying up to date on any regulations that may impact the organization and its employees are all part of HR's responsibilities. E-HRM facilitates human resource functions with the chance to create new avenues for committing to organizational success. HRM

activity; not only complementing it, but often even substituting it. In order to meet the demands of today's knowledge-based economy, it is almost a must for companies to maximize the potential and productivity of their employees, a goal towards which HRM information systems and E-HRM could be of help. E-HRM is an advance business solution which provides a complete on-line support in the management of all processes, activities, data and information required to manage human resources in a modern company. An HR department's job is to increase employee productivity while also protecting the organization from any problems that develop in the workplace. Compensation and benefits, recruitment, dismissal, and staying up to date on any regulations that may affect the organization and its employees are all part of HR's responsibilities.

Recommendation and Suggestion

- New technologies will use in HR management include Artificial Intelligence, machine learning, and Virtual Reality.
- Successful organizations harness these and a range of proven digital tools within a market-leading HR management system.
- It is possible to expand the research. From recruitment to engagement to people management, artificial intelligence algorithms are revolutionizing a variety of HR processes.
- Cloud-based HR technology to support a global workforce that is becoming increasingly remote and gig-based.
- The HR industry will have been able to advance towards thought leadership through the application of technology and people analytics

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